

COLOUR AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF MANGANOUS SULPHIDE.

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In this work the magnetic susceptibilities of the green and the pink varieties of manganous sulphide have been measured on a Gouy's balance. It is shown that the cubic B₃ type and the hexagonal B₄ type modifications of the pink sulphide have more or less the same susceptibility value, whereas the green modification gives a much higher χ -value. The cause of these differences is discussed. Measurement of susceptibilities of the different preparations of MnS at different temperatures indicate that the Curie-Weiss law is applicable in their case.

It is generally recognised that manganous sulphide exists in two forms: rose and green. The grey variety reported in earlier literature has been shown to consist of the rose and the green varieties in varying proportions. The two forms are identical in composition (Antony and Donnini, *Gazzetta*, 1893, **23**, 560) but the difference in colour, density and particle size of the two preparations is so marked that they are usually assumed to represent two isomeric forms. As numerous cases are known where differences in colour, density, etc., are due to differences in physical state of the same substance, the question arises whether the transformation from rose to green manganous sulphide is due to a change in physical character or in molecular structure.

The magnetic method has recently afforded useful information on the structure of particularly the paramagnetic compounds. In general, if the electronic orbits of an atom are so disposed that their resultant magnetic moment is zero, the atom exhibits diamagnetism, whereas paramagnetic behaviour is the consequence of a resultant magnetic moment. Van Vleck ("Theory of Electric and Magnetic Susceptibilities", Oxford, particularly Chapter XI, p. 73), Sommerfeld ("Atombau," 4th Ed. p. 639), Bose (*Z. Physik*, 1927, **43**, 864) and Stoner (*Phil. Mag.*, 1929, **8**, 250) have obtained the following derivation:

$$\mu_B = \sqrt{4s(s+1) + l(l+1)}$$

which reduces to

$$\mu_B = \sqrt{4s(s+1)}$$

where l , the orbital moment, is fully quenched.

The paramagnetic salts of the transition metals give magnetic values which are, more or less, in accord with the theoretical values deduced on Van Vleck's formula for spin. The sulphides, however, have not been investigated so completely and systematically from the magnetic standpoint. There are often considerable differences in values found by different workers for the susceptibility of a particular sulphide and there are few precise determinations of the change of χ with temperature. Thus according to Wedekind (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1924, **37**, 87) manganous sulphide has a susceptibility value of 44.32×10^{-6} but according to Wistrand ("Magnetiska susceptibiliteten hos kvarts, Tellur och Nagra Halmium fereringara", Upsala, 1916) this value is 64.8×10^{-6} . Haraldsen and Klemm (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, **220**, 183) recently investigated the influence of temperature on its susceptibility and concluded that the susceptibility value approaches that calculated for manganous ion as the temperature is raised. Work on similar lines has been done by Mehmed and Haraldsen (*ibid.*, 1938, **235**, 193).

The observed susceptibility values of MnS are widely different from the theoretical values calculated on the Bose-Stoner formula for spin. It may be that these deviations are due to wide divergence from the Curie law,

$\chi_M = \frac{C_M}{T}$ and the magnetic behaviour of MnS is better represented by its

Weiss modification, $\chi_M = \frac{C_M}{T - \theta}$, since the divergence arises primarily from distortions produced by interatomic forces, etc., and these are taken into consideration in the Weiss law by the introduction of θ . The Bohr magneton number can be evaluated from the relationship,

$$\mu_B = 2.839 \sqrt{\chi_M(T - \theta)}.$$

The present work was undertaken in order to study the magnetic behaviour of sulphides at different temperatures and to determine, if possible, whether the transformation from the rose to the green modification involves, a physical change or a molecular rearrangement.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The sulphide was prepared in two colours: rose and green.

Rose Sulphides.

(I) Equal volume of M -MnCl₂ and 1.35M-NH₄HS were mixed together. The rose-coloured manganous sulphide so formed was washed with water

containing a little H_2S until free of chloride and sulphide. It was then washed six times with 20 c.c. portions of alcohol, twice with carbon disulphide and finally 3 more times with alcohol. The product was dried at 60° in an atmosphere of dry and purified hydrogen sulphide (Weiser and Milligan, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **35**, 2330).

(II) Equimolecular quantities of $M-MnCl_2$ and $2M$ -sodium sulphide were mixed. The product was washed and dried as described above.

Green Sulphides.

(I) Purified and dried H_2S was passed over the rose variety at 320° . The green sulphide so formed was washed with carbon disulphide to free it of any free sulphur and dried at 60° (Antony and Donnini, *loc. cit.*).

(II) Hydrogen sulphide was passed over manganous sulphate heated to 600° . The green sulphide so formed was washed with carbon disulphide to free it of sulphur, if any, and dried.

(III) 20 C.c. of $M-MnCl_2$, 25 c.c. of 11.6 $M-NH_4OH$, 30 c.c. of 1.35 $M-NH_4HS$ and 45 c.c. of water were mixed together. The green product began developing in a few minutes. It was left in contact with the solution for a few days when whole of the product turned green. It was washed and dried (Weiser and Milligan, *loc. cit.*).

Analysis.—Manganese was estimated by the pyrophosphate method. Sulphide was oxidised to sulphate with bromine and nitric acid, the sulphate precipitated as $BaSO_4$, washed, ignited and weighed. The results of these analyses are given in Table I which also records the densities of the samples.

TABLE I.

Reading.	Modification of MnS .	Density at 33° .	M a n g a n e s e		S u l p h u r	
			Expt.	Theor.	Expt.	Theor.
1	Rose I	3.246	63.12%	63.22%	36.79%	36.78%
2	„ II	3.250	63.16	„	36.73	„
3	Green I	3.970	63.22	„	36.81	„
4	„ II	3.965	63.18	„	36.77	„
5	„ III	4.012	63.20	„	36.75	„

Magnetic Data.

The magnetic susceptibility value of the samples was determined on a modified form of Gouy's magnetic balance.

For measurements at higher temperatures an electrically heated silica tube-furnace was used. The variations in temperature near the pole pieces on account of the furnace were not found to affect the field strength, because the pull per gram observed for a standard diamagnetic at various temperatures was found to be unaffected. In order to see whether the substance in the tube had actually attained the temperature recorded by the thermometer in the electric furnace, a magnetic examination of manganese pyrophosphate, prepared from analytically pure manganese sulphate, was undertaken. The calculation of temperature was made by the aid of the Curie-Weiss law, $\chi_M = \frac{C_M}{T - \theta}$, the value of $\theta(-23^\circ)$ being known for this compound. The observed and the calculated temperatures are tabulated below.

TABLE II.

Reading.	$\chi \times 10^6$.	Temperature °K.	
		Obs.	Calc.
1	101.73	305	—
2	95.80	325	325.3
3	88.20	355	355.3
4	76.30	414	414.3
5	68.70	463	462.7

The agreement between the two values is excellent.

The magnetic results are recorded in Table III. The value of μ_B is calculated from the formula

$$\mu_B = 2.839 \sqrt{\chi_M (T - \theta)}$$

where χ_M corresponding to the observed χ is calculated for one metallic atom per molecule and θ , the Curie point, is determined by plotting $1/\chi$, T graph and reading off θ as the intercept on the T -axis.

TABLE III.

Preparation.

ROSE I.

Reading.	Temp.	$\chi \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	θ .	C_M .	Mean	
						C_M .	μ_B .
1	307°K	41·95	3650		4·478		
2	336	40·97	3564		4·477		
3	367	40·02	3482		4·482		
				-920°K		4·488	6·02
4	410	38·72	3369		4·481		
5	460	37·36	3250		4·485		
6	510	36·37	3164		4·525		

ROSE II.

1	307	41·80	3637		4·389		
2	338	40·80	3550		4·394		
3	370	39·80	3463		4·398		
				-900°K		4·394	5·95
4	417	38·45	3335		4·391		
5	480	36·71	3194		4·409		
6	518	35·50	3089		4·381		

GREEN I.

1	307	64·15	5581		4·487		
2	337	61·80	5377		4·484		
3	367	59·63	5188		4·482		
				-497°K		4·475	6·01
4	417	56·30	4898		4·477		
5	477	52·78	4592		4·472		
6	510	51·04	4440		4·472		

TABLE III (contd.).

GREEN II.							
Reading.	Temp.	$\chi \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	θ .	C_M .	Mean C_M .	μ_B .
1	307°K	64.20	5585		4.462		
2	337	61.90	5385		4.465		
3	365	59.86	5208		4.464		
				-492°K		4.462	6.00
4	411	56.50	4916		4.469		
5	483	52.62	4578		4.464		
6	507	51.20	4454		4.450		
GREEN III.							
1	307	64.10	5577		4.462		
2	337	61.70	5368		4.455		
3	366	59.51	5177		4.447		
				-493°K		4.448	5.99
4	417	56.21	4890		4.450		
5	483	52.30	4550		4.441		
6	510	50.81	4420		4.434		

DISCUSSION.

Prominent points which the foregoing investigation brings forth are :

(i) That the samples of the rose sulphide have a susceptibility value of $41.85 (\pm 0.10) \times 10^{-6}$ at 34°C . The $(1/\chi, T)$ graph gives a θ value of $-910^\circ \pm 10^\circ$ and the magneton number calculated on the Curie-Weiss formula works out to $5.95 - 6.02$ which is in good accord with the theoretical value of 5.92 , found for bivalent manganese on Van Vleck's formula for spin.

(ii) That the samples of the green sulphide prepared (1) by precipitation method, (2) by passing hydrogen sulphide over the rose sulphide and (3) by passing H_2S over manganous sulphate, gave χ value of $64.15 (\pm 0.05) \times 10^{-6}$. The Curie temperature was found to be -495 ± 3 . The magnetic moment is $5.99 - 6.01$ which again is in excellent agreement with the calculated value.

The two varieties exhibit varying shades of colour. The green modification exhibits light green to dark green shades and yet it is remarkable that the different samples give practically the same susceptibility value which

suggests that the varying colour shades are due to differences in particle size which has been shown by Bhatnagar and co-workers (Bhatnagar, Verma and Haq, *Kolloid Z.*, 1937, **78**, 9 ; Lessheim, *Current Sci.*, 1936, **5**, 119) to have little effect on the susceptibility. In this connection, it is of interest to note that Weiser and Milligan (*loc. cit*) arrived at a similar conclusion from X-ray analysis of the different preparations of green MnS. They found the X-radiograms of the different specimens to be identical. The crystals had NaCl-type lattice and the value of a_0 for the crystals (whether light or dark green) was found to be 5.20 Å. Hence they concluded that the differences in shade do not involve changes in crystal structure but are dependent on difference in particle size.

Schnaase (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, **B20**, 89) recently carried out an X-ray examination of manganous sulphides and concluded that the sulphide exists in three modifications. The green sulphide has NaCl-lattice structure and the rose sulphide is, in general, a mixture of two modifications one of which has the zinc blende lattice (cubic B₃ type) and the other one the Wurtzit lattice (hexagonal B₄ type). Since the preparations (I) and (II) of the rose sulphide have been obtained by different chemical methods, they may be expected to contain the two modifications in different proportions and if susceptibility were influenced by the crystal structure, then the hexagonal type ought to have a different susceptibility from the cubic B₃ type with the result that the two preparations will give different χ values. The values for the two samples, however, are more or less the same. It, therefore, appears that change in crystal structure cannot be responsible, except perhaps to a very small extent, for the divergence noticed between the χ values of the rose and the green sulphides. The cause of this divergence in colour and susceptibility is rather to be sought in possible differences in the type of linkage involved in the two cases, but as the data on the band spectroscopy of manganese compounds are scanty, it is not possible to say how exactly the linkages differ in the two cases.

Incidentally it may be mentioned here that the density of the sulphides calculated from the X-ray analysis of Schnaase are 4.056, 3.289 and 3.780 respectively for the green, red (cubic) and red (hexagonal) modifications and these values are in fairly good accord with the experimental values recorded in Table I, which is indicative of the correctness of the X-ray data of Schnaase.

As regards the theoretical interpretation of θ , it is quite clear that it is not an atomic property but is due primarily to distortions produced by inter-atomic forces arising partly from the Heisenberg's exchange effect (Van Vleck, "Theory of Electric and Magnetic Susceptibilities", Oxford,

Chapter XII) and partly from the interaction of the orbital angular momentum. The Mn^{++} ion, as in MnS , is in the S-state and consequently devoid of any orbital angular momentum. Hence in this case θ value should be dependent entirely on Heisenberg exchange effect. This is actually shown to be the case with hydrated sulphates where the effect of exchange forces vanish on account of high "magnetic dilution" and as expected θ has zero value. The sulphides of transition elements, however, have very high "magnetic concentration" compared to the salts composed of a variety of atoms and it is, therefore, not surprising that the magnetic susceptibility of MnS deviates widely from the Curie law. It is also possible that some other disturbing influence, *e.g.*, crystalline field effects, etc., may be operating at the same time. It is, however, not possible to obtain a quantitative interpretation of θ on the concept of intrinsic molecular fields or distortions arising from interatomic forces. Nevertheless, the importance of this determination in explaining the anomalous magnetic behaviour of sulphides is clearly brought out.

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Received July 7, 1939.

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